

A STUDY OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE IN THE UNIVERSITY SECTOR

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Abstract

Universities understand that Quality of Work Life is important to their employees. Quality of Work Life is really a big factor for employees because it brings enjoyment while working in the university which in turns brings happiness in life. It is the responsibility of the management to fulfill the needs of administrative staff, so they can work with full efficiency. This is also important to assess the level of Quality of Work Life of administrative staff. So the primary objective of this study is to assess the level of Quality of Work Life of administrative staff working in Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak (PBDSUHS). The tool employed for generating responses will questionnaire based survey of administrative staff to their perception and opinion towards different factors of Quality of Work Life. This study indicates that Quality of Work Life of administrative staff is important and it is necessary to improve the Quality of Work Life by fulfilling the needs of administrative staff.

Key Words: *Quality of work life, job security, job Satisfaction, work life balance*

Paper Type Research Paper

Poor Quality of Work Life lead to low morale and administrative staff cannot do the work with full efficiency. The inefficiency makes hurdles in their growth and development and decrease performance of university. Administrative Staff have difficulties in meeting the needs of teaching faculty and students if their own Quality of Work Life is not good. The job of administrative staff requires a fulltime and efficiency in university. If administrative staff is satisfied with the factors of Quality of Work Life then they are easily motivated and fulfill the personal as well as university's objective.

Objective

The present study attempts to achieve the following objective:

- To assess the level of quality of work life of administrative staff of Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak .

Justification of Study

The researcher has taken two things in mind while doing research, first is that administrative staff deserve to be treated fairly. Secondly, good Quality of Work Life can increase productivity of administrative staff and it increases efficiency of university.

Research Methodology

(a) Research Instrument

Adopted questionnaire is used as a research instrument. The instrument uses —5- point likert scale from: 1-strongly agree, 2-agree, 3-neither agree nor disagree, 4-Disagree, 5-strongly disagree. Questionnaire is administered to administrative staff in Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak. This questionnaire shows the opinions of administrative staff in regard to each question. The questionnaire included 40 statements added by some personal questions. 4 open ended questions relate to comments, problems, expectation of new policy and suggestions to improve on quality of work life. By combining all these questions the study enables to take an in depth sight of quality of work life of every university. The data collection has been done in primary form by the

investigators. The data is analyzed with the help of Mean, Standard Deviation and percentage.

(b) Sample

To select the respondents, the study makes use of non probabilistic sampling methods. The sampling methods used were a mix of judgmental and convenient sampling. Sample size of this study is 100.

Results and Discussion

Table I : Descriptive Statistics

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1. Working atmosphere	100	4.19	.526	25	69	6	0	0
2. I feel pride in working with the university.	100	4.86	.349	86	14	0	0	0
3. University provides facility for the self improvement of their non teaching employees.	100	3.56	.556	0	59	38	3	0
4. The chances for promotion are good.	100	3.85	.557	0	91	6	0	3
5. I have each and every facility that I need to do my work right.	100	3.67	.726	12	46	39	3	0
6. I am satisfied with my job.	100	3.88	.729	18	55	24	3	0
7. At work, my opinions seem to count.	100	3.89	.490	7	75	18	0	0

8. Promotions are handled fairly.	100	3.88	.640	15	58	27	0	0
9. I am aware of the daily operations within my department.	100	4.13	.597	25	63	12	0	0
1. I feel certain restrictions in my work area.	100	2.48	.703	0	3	51	37	9
2. My university is having positive attitude towards me.	100	4.27	.446	27	73	0	0	0
3. My supervisor is helpful to me in getting the job done.	100	4.43	.607	49	45	6	0	0
4. University enhances self esteem and dignity of workers.	100	4.01	.611	19	63	18	0	0
5. When I do my job well, I am likely to be praised by my supervisor or employer.	100	3.82	.626	12	58	30	0	0
6. I feel that the income from my job alone is enough to meet my family's usual monthly expenses and bills.	100	3.93	.820	24	51	19	6	0
7. I maintain balance between work and family life.	100	4.00	.492	12	76	12	0	0
8. An opportunity provided by the job for the development of the non teaching employee is satisfactory.	100	3.67	.473	0	67	33	0	0
9. Sometimes I feel stressful and overloaded.	100	2.60	.816	9	12	45	34	0
10. University improves the physical and emotional well being of its employees.	100	3.82	.386	0	82	18	0	0
11. On my job, I know exactly what is expected from me.	100	4.28	.514	31	66	3	0	0
12. At the place where I work, I am respected.	100	4.52	.502	52	48	0	0	0
13. I trust the management at the place where I work.	100	4.21	.478	24	73	3	0	0

14.	In my job, I take part with others in making decisions that affect me.	100	3.88	.640	12	67	18	3	0
15.	I get correct information about my work, duties, responsibility and authorities.	100	4.13	.485	19	75	6	0	0
16.	In the last seven days, I received recognition or praise for doing good work.	100	3.32	.839	9	29	47	15	0
17.	I have authority and responsibility regarding my job.	100	3.91	.570	12	67	21	0	0
18.	I am appraised for my best performance.	100	4.03	.388	9	85	6	0	0
19.	I am satisfied with the formal evaluation process in my unit.	100	3.97	.460	9	79	12	0	0
20.	I am usually satisfied with the way in which I balance my professional and personal life.	100	3.64	.689	0	76	12	12	0
21.	I am satisfied with the working environment provided by the university.	100	3.95	.500	7	84	6	3	0
22.	I feel free to offer comments and suggestions to my colleagues as well as my authority/management.	100	3.78	.645	12	54	34	0	0
23.	University does a good job of linking rewards with job performance.	100	3.93	.607	12	72	13	3	0
24.	Idea given by me that brings changes in the organization is appreciated.	100	3.27	.446	0	27	73	0	0
25.	I usually get opportunities to improve my job.	100	3.61	.695	0	73	15	12	0
1.	Working Life in this university is satisfactory.	100	3.79	.591	0	88	3	9	0

2.	All the members of the university have the sense of one community.	100	2.54	1.077	0	31	6	49	14
3.	In university almost everyone knows who is working under whom.	100	3.85	.833	19	53	25	0	3
4.	Seniors/authorities pay attention to complaints of juniors/ subordinates.	100	3.67	.533	0	70	27	3	0
5.	My job enhances my social prestige.	100	3.98	.402	7	84	9	0	0
6.	The future of Quality of Work Life is bright	100	3.67	.682	0	79	9	12	0
Valid N (list wise)		100							

The data were analyzed to answer the following questions:

How does administrative staff perceive the quality of work life at University?

How is administrative staff spending their time and how would they prefer to spend it?

Table 1 shows the mean, percentage, and standard deviation in respect of quality of work life in Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak. In assessing the level of Quality of Work Life 40 corresponding items were identified in the questionnaire and the respondents' perception in selected university was accordingly scored. According to the table, the mean score for item 1 is 4.19 which depicts a higher level of cleanliness and transparency in working atmosphere. Results of data analysis show clearly that the quality of work life prevailing in university is actually pleasant. The implication of this is that the university is generally committed to promoting the development of administrative staff by providing a conducive environment for them to learn. Specifically, item (2) with mean score of 4.86 revealed that administrative staff feels pride in working with the university. The quality of work life in university is very good. Employees feel that the kind of work which they got to do is quite good. Being a new university, there is huge scope of improvement and administration is working hard in this direction.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to investigate the prevalent Quality of Work Life in Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak. On the basis of the above discussion, it may be concluded that the quality of work life in university is very good. These findings can help the policy makers to formulate strategy about quality of work life and hence increase the productivity.

References

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